

Assessment of Maintenance Practices for Business Education Modern Facilities in Rivers State Universities

Wogboroma Nyemaekile (Ph.D) & Nwosu Rose Yeyeda(Ph.D)

Department of Business Education, Faculty of Education

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Corresponding Authors' Email: wogboroma.nyemaekile@ust.edu.ng & roseyeyeda@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study assessed Business education modern facilities maintenance practices for effective utilization in teaching Business education programme in Universities in Rivers State. Three purpose of study, three research questions and one hypothesis were used to guide the study. The population comprised of 122 Business Education lecturers in Universities in Rivers State. Based on the size of the population, the whole population was used for the study. The main instrument for data collection was questionnaire titled "Plant Facilities maintenance practices for effective utilization in teaching Business Education Programme Questionnaire" (PPMEUTBEPQ)" and data collected were face and content validated by three lecturers, two from Business Education and the other from measurement and evaluation all in the Faculty of Education, Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Test-retest method was used to arrive at 0.9 indicating that the instrument has a high reliability. Out of 122 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 96 were retrieved and used for the study. Decision rule was based on the four point Likert Rating Scale of Strongly agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree(SD) respectively. Twenty Questionnaires (20) were raised from the research questions and was analyzed using a four point Likert Scale. The hypothesis was tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance. The data collected were analyzed using Mean method and Standard Deviation. A benchmark of 2.5 was used as a criterion for agreement. It was concluded from the study that the items on predictive, preventive and routine maintenance were all agreed by the staff in Business education universities in Rivers State. The following recommendations were made among others that: Government of Rivers State should encourage a maintenance culture among staff and students in Business Education department.

Keywords: Modern facilities, Maintenance Practice, Business Education Programme

INTRODUCTION

School facilities are available in various forms. The plants may be movable or fixed assets that serve various functions in the learning environment (Agenyi, Cletus & Agenyi, 2015). School facilities are vital instruments for implementing educational programme. School administrators and teachers have important roles to play in developing and making them function effectively. Their effectiveness in the implementation of business education programme, meeting the physical needs of a school and their impact on teacher's utilization depends on its physical condition or quality of plant facilities maintenance.

Business education is a branch of education that involves teaching the skills and operations of the business industry. This field of education occurs at multiple levels, including secondary and higher education institutes. Education in business has many forms, mainly occurring within a classroom of a school. A business education has many components such as accounting, office technology and management education (OTME), marketing and Entrepreneurship as there are many different areas of the business industries as a whole. An education in business varies greatly in its curriculum and popularity around the world. development is often an integral part of an education in business. Business education generally refers to the plethora of courses designed to provide students with any number of skills needed for success in business,

especially those related to launching and running businesses (Akeke, Oche, Akuegwu & Ushie, 2022). Bilyaminu in Godspower and Ekpo (2021) defined Business education is an aspect of the total education programme which provides the recipients with the knowledge, skills, attitudes and understanding needed to perform in the business world, either as a producer and/or as a consumer of goods and services. The essence of business education is for acquisition of required skills and knowledge to enable recipients fit into the business world. Furthermore, Akpan describes Business Education as a skill-based programme that trains students for office careers or occupations and for entrepreneurship, as distributors of goods and services, or as users of information (Okolocha & Nwadiani, 2015). Hence, Ogonu (2019) asserts that business education definitions center on the acquisition of skills that will enable the learners on graduation become saleable by gaining either paid employment or establishing a business education and become self reliant. Thus, the quality of Business education programme in Nigeria is hinged upon the skills pedagogical strategies and the adequacy of plant facilities adopted by lecturers for effective School plant facilities according to Ololube (2013) consist of the basic systems and structures which are what the schools or institutions need in order to function effectively and fulfill the purposes for which they were established. Ololube, further said that school plants include the followings:

building, equipment, machinery, furniture, electrical infrastructure, water supply infrastructure and their correspondent components. Xaba (2022), sees school plants as the space and physical resources which the school administrator and his reference groups harness, allocate, utilize and maintain for the purpose of effective school administration. Xaba (2022) also pointed out that school site, which is the landscapes on which the school's permanent and non-permanent structures are built, are part of school plants. They also include buildings, equipment, and furniture, vehicles of various types, electrical fittings, books, water supply infrastructures and accessories like playground, lawns, parks and farms as parts of schools Plants. The author further affirmed that learning facilities such as furniture, chalkboard, tools and machine, generating plant, chalk, cars, trucks, computer sets, typewriters, audio and visual aid, bores holes are necessary tools in the school programme teaching delivery.

Maintenance as an ongoing process is always necessary in any school plant whether well built, furnished or equipped. According to Ivor (2012), maintenance is "the combination of all technical and associated administrative actions intended to retain an item in, or restore it to, a state in which it can perform maximally. Gahlot (2015) defines maintenance as a process of keeping equipment/facilities in good working condition for its efficient and effective use in production. According to Oguche (2021), maintenance of school plants is the keeping of the buildings, equipment and landscape at its best condition of completeness and efficiency either through repairs or replacement. It is necessary to put some staff in charge of maintenance of building and equipment to avoid fast damage and depreciation. One of the needs of maintaining school plants is that the school environment and the activities that take place in it must be considered healthy and productive. The physical appearance of school plants tells one how good the school is in terms of maintaining of facilities and learning. Isaac and Musibau (2010) asserts that poorly is maintained school plants (derelict buildings. untidy walls and over grown weeds in the compounds) may suggest that the education within the building follow the same pattern. A common trend in the use of facilities in Nigeria that when new facilities and equipment are installed and taken over by the appropriate authorities for use, little or no maintenance attention is paid to such facilities. This implies that maintenance strategies are action plans put in place to maintain an item, equipment/machinery, structure

etc. Maintenance strategies of schools' plants could be in form of predictive, preventive, routine and corrective maintenance.

According to Ogbuanya (2019), predictive maintenance is the type of maintenance that is carried out on a building, an item or equipment when there is breakdown warning. It involves the use of computer software and visual inspection to predict possible failures in an item Possible task that could be seen are using vibration analysis to predict possible Faults in an item, using visual inspection to predict when sporting kits should be maintained, using visual inspection to evaluate the condition of teaching aids and using visual inspection to predict when to clear the grasses in the surrounding of the schools. Preventive maintenance follows immediately fault has been predicted in school plants. Ihuoma (2018) stated that preventive maintenance is that type of maintenance carried out on facilities to avoid breakdown and ensure optimal performances of the facilities. Up to date information about the facility is required to serve as a guide for the maintenance team. It saves cost and time. Activities involved are regular cleaning of laboratory equipment, replacement of worn-out part of any machinery of school plants, periodic cutting of grasses in school compound, periodic inspections of teaching aids and periodic clearing of stationery equipment in the library etc. School plants can be prevented from damage through routine maintenance.

Routine maintenance according to Ihuoma (2018) is the work or activities necessary to keep facilities in good operating condition. The maintenance work may be done daily, weekly, or monthly depending on the agreed schedules. Manufacturers' guides provide information on the nature and maintenance intervals. Activities such as cleaning washrooms, grading roads and mowing lawns, maintenance and replacement of doors and windows locks, replacement of bulletin board etc. make up routine maintenance. Corrective maintenance is followed up immediately facilities are being damaged, which may be in form of repairs or replacements in the school plants.

Corrective maintenance can also be referred to as breakdown maintenance. It is the kind of maintenance given to equipment or facilities when they fail to function optimally. It is a response given to unanticipated problems or emergencies (Emenalo, 2017). Corrective maintenance include failure identification of faulty part of machinery/equipment by experts in school plant workshops, shut down of machinery and equipment for

repairs, replacement of damaged parts of faulty items, repair of faulty items, etc, in school plants.

Utilization of school plant facilities in Business education as been a basic factor due to the nature of the programme been a skilled based course. Scholars over decades has constantly investigated on plant facilities needed for effective teaching of Business education programme such as Acharu, F. T. & Solomon, E. (2014) Influence of infrastructure on the teaching and learning of office education in Polytechnics., Ayelotan, and Sholagbade (2014). Infrastructural facilities and business education: Office technology and management perspective, Bongotons, and Onyenwe (2020). Availability and adequacy of ICT resources in business education program in Nigeria, Nwokocha and Onwuchekwa (2014). A survey on interactive whiteboard (IWB) usage and perception of business education lecturers and students among others.

But none as concentrated on plant maintenance facilities in teaching Business education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It is this gap identified that this study intends to fill.

Statement of Problem

Business education infrastructure in universities plays a crucial role in providing students with a conducive learning environment. These facilities are meant to be adequately provided by the appropriate authorities and meticulously handled relevant stakeholders in order to ensure that it serves out its purpose of brings about the promotion of a healthy environment where teaching and learning can thrive. However, the maintenance culture of these facilities is often neglected, leading to deterioration and inefficiency. More so, the obvious reality as regards state of universities facilities in Business Education are becoming more worrisome as some universities in Rivers State experience high level of inadequacies in school plant availability and functionality (Xaba, 2022). Even in some universities where these school plants like the classroom blocks and instructional resources are being relatively provided, they are not properly used in order to ensure it serves it purpose of bringing about positive teaching and learning process.

The researchers have observed overtime that plant facilities in Business education are quite inadequate has some teachers are seen to be teaching without relevant instructional materials and at the right plant facility while students are subjected to the level of learning in overcrowded classrooms which in turn might not yield effective utilization of plant facilities. However, the

researchers been concerned about this development investigated into plant facilities maintenance for effective utilization in teaching Business education programme in Rivers State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of the study is to assess plant facilities maintenance culture for effective utilization in teaching Business education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Specifically, the study intends to determine;

1. predictive maintenance strategies for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State.
2. routine maintenance strategies for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State.
3. corrective maintenance strategies for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the predictive maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State?
2. What are the routine maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State?
3. What are the corrective maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was tested:

There is no significance difference in the mean rating of maintenance culture and effective utilization of facilities for teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive survey research was adopted for this study. The population of this study comprised of one hundred and twenty-two (122) business education lecturers from universities in Rivers State (Business Education Departments, 2024). Based on the size and proximity of the respondent to the researcher, the whole population were sampled. The tool for data collection used in the study was questionnaire titled: “Plant Facilities Maintenance culture for Effective Utilization in Teaching Business Education Programme Questionnaire (PFCMEUTBEPQ)”. However, the instrument has two sections: Sections A and B respectively. Section A deals with demographic data of the respondents such as department, title and Sex. However, Section B is made up of items on the problem of the study. Similarly, the instrument was structured on a modified 4-point likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) (4.0), Agree (A) (3.0), Strongly Disagree (SD) (2.0) and Disagree (1.0). To

ensure the validity of the instrument for this study, the draft questionnaire was given to three experts in Measurement and Evaluation, and Business education who were from Rivers State University. To determine the reliability of the instrument, the questionnaire was subjected to test-retest method of reliability which yielded 0.79 co-efficient. 122 questionnaires were distributed and 96 were retrieved and used for the study. Data collected on demographic information of respondents were analyzed using descriptive statistic of mean and standard deviation. And the hypothesis was tested using z-test at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question One: What are the predictive maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Predictive Maintenance Strategies Needed for Improving Plant Facilities Utilization in Teaching Business Education Programme in Universities in Rivers State N=96

S/N	Items	X ₁	SD	Decision
1.	Using vibration analysis to predict possible fault in an equipment	3.5	.89	Strongly Agree
2.	Using visual inspection to predict when to clear the grasses in the surrounding of the school	2.9	.53	agree
3.	Using visual inspection to evaluate the condition of teaching aids.	3.1	.42	Agree
4.	Using visual inspection to predict then stationeries materials should he renewed	3.0	.79	Agree
5.	Using visual inspection to predict when dust should be removed from electrical appliances and furniture in the school	3.5	.63	Strongly Agree
Grand mean		3.2	0.7	Agree

Source: field survey, 2024

Table 1 shows the result of data analysis stating that the overall mean rating of the respondents ranges was 3.2 and standard deviation was 0.7 indicating that the respondents agreed that predictive maintenance strategies are needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State

Research Question Two: What are the routing maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Routine Maintenance Strategies Needed for Improving Plant Facilities Utilization in Teaching Business Education Programme in Universities in Rivers State N=96

S/N	Items	X ₁	SD	Decision
1.	Replacement of bulletin board.	2.8	.73	Agree
2.	Replacement of building directories	3.6	.89	Strongly agree
3.	Check the condition of incoming service wires and support of electrical component	3.5	.72	Strongly agree
4.	Check whether fuses or circuit breakers trip frequently.	3.1	.66	Agree
5.	Inspect the water supply and waste pipes for rust and leaks in the	3.2	.63	Agree

school building

Grand mean **3.2** **0.7** **Agree**

Source: field survey, 2024

Table 2 shows the result of data analysis stating that the overall mean rating of the respondents was 3.2 and standard deviation was 0.7 indicating that the respondents agreed that routine maintenance strategies are needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State

Research Question three: What are the corrective maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of corrective maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State N=92

S/N	Items	X ₁	SD	Decision
1.	Identification of faulty parts of machinery/equipment by expert in school plant laboratories	3.8	.73	Agree
2.	Identification of faulty ICT equipment for maintenance.	3.9	.89	Strongly agree
3.	Identification of damaged part of school building for correction.	3.4	.72	Strongly agree
4.	Tag caution sign during corrective maintenance	3.7	.66	Agree
5.	Reassemble of dismantled equipment or items.	3.8	.63	Agree
Grand mean		3.7	0.7	Agree

Source: field survey, 2024

Table 3 shows the result of data analysis stating that the overall mean rating of the respondents ranges from 2.7 to 3.6 indicating that the respondents agreed that all the aforementioned are the plausible solution facing administrations of business education on staff job performance in universities in Rivers State.

Testing of hypotheses

HO₁: There is no difference in the mean rating of maintenance culture and effective utilization of facilities for teaching Business education programme in tertiary institutions' Rivers State.

Table 4: Independent z-test Comparison of Mean Response of Maintenance Culture and Effective Utilization of Facilities for Teaching Business Education Programme in Tertiary Institutions' Rivers State

Respondents	N	X	SD	DF	Level of Sig.	z-cal	z-crit	Decision
Maintenance culture	48	2.36	0.68	90	0.05	1.131	1.960	Accept HO ₁
Business education	48	3.42	0.71					

Source: Field work, (2024)

Data in Table 4 show that the calculated z-value of 1.131 at 90 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of significance is low than the critical value of 1.960. This shows that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of maintenance culture and effective utilization of facilities for teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Predictive maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State

Table 1 shows the result of data analysis stating that the overall mean rating of the respondents ranges was 3.2 and standard deviation was 0.7 indicating that the respondents agreed that predictive maintenance strategies are needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching

Business education programme in universities This study is related to the study of Agenyi and Cletus (2012), that predictive maintenance is seen to be the best as it involves the use of modern-day computer software to predict equipment age, manufacturing fault, user demands, quality control and performance indices in order to predict when maintenance should be performed. This in essence shows that the school will be a better place to acquire knowledge if maintenance is regularly carried out.

Routine maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State

Table 2 shows the result of data analysis stating that the overall mean rating of the respondents was 3.2 and standard deviation was 0.7 indicating that the respondents agreed that routing maintenance strategies are needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. This study is related to the study of Agengi & Cletus (2012) that certain equipment like computer, Internet facilities, typewriter, servicing generator and other items in the school require periodic servicing by the school administrators (Principals), the servicing may be monthly, quarterly, yearly or as the condition of the facility may require often the manufacturers guide provide information on the nature and maintenance intervals. Ihuoma (2018) also added that routine maintenance is carried out periodically as scheduled by the school managers and may be serviced monthly, quarterly or even annually depending on the agreed schedule. This in essence shows that school plants in Rivers west education zone can be maintain by the itemized activities on routine maintenance.

Corrective maintenance strategies needed for improving plant facilities utilization in teaching Business education programme in universities in Rivers State

Table 3 shows the result of data analysis stating that the overall mean rating of the respondents ranges from 2.7 to 3.6 indicating that the respondents agreed that all the aforementioned are the plausible solution facing administrations of business education lecturers in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. This study is related to the study of Etuk (2017) who stated that corrective maintenance is also known as reaction maintenance which involves all unscheduled actions performed as a result of system failure like the school plants

CONCLUSION

School plant maintenance is a major responsibility of the administrators and staff in school. This is because they are the direct user of the school plant facilities. Based be carried out in the school plant facilities to ensure proper teaching of Business education programme takes place, so that the studenton the findings, the items on predictive, preventive and routine maintenance were all agreed by the staff in Business education in universities in Rivers State. Agreed in the sense that their mean scores were above the average of 2.50. The findings showed that all the strategies listed should s, teachers and the government achieve its aims/objectives.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made.

1. Government of Rivers State should encourage a maintenance culture among staff and students in Business Education department
2. The management of these universities should provide training and development programme for maintenance personnel to enhance their skills and knowledge
3. The management of these universities should implement a preventive maintenance programme to prevent equipment failure and reduce downtime

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